

List of Supplemental Tables and Figures

Table S1. Stocking rates for each site. Grazed sites had stocking rates of 1 cow/4,047 m² and are grazed year-round.

^aSite 5 has a stocking rate of 0 but experienced occasional trespass grazing, sometimes for a significant amount of time.

Site	Grazing Level	Stocking Rate
G1	Grazed	1 cow/ 4,047 m ² year-round
G2	Grazed	1 cow/ 4,047 m ² year-round
G3	Grazed	1 cow/ 4,047 m ² year-round
LG1	Lightly Grazed	0
LG2 ^a	Lightly Grazed	0

Table S2. Densities of tarantula burrows and hawk wasps by site, including lower and upper 95% confidence limits. Adjustments used in fitting the parametric ‘key’ to the perpendicular distance function estimated by DISTANCE (Thomas *et al.*, 2010)

Grazing Level	Site	Tarantula Burrow Density (Ha) (95% CI)	Hawk Wasp Density (Ha) (95% CI)
Grazed	G1	297.6 (244.5,362.1)	11.3 (9.1,13.9)
	G2	621.0 (516.2,746.9)	4.7 (3.9,5.5)
	G3	318.6 (245.1,414.1)	6.6 (5.3,8.4)
Lightly Grazed	LG1	86.3 (62.9,118.5)	55.2 (34.6,88.2)
	LG2	89.3 (64.5,123.6)	41.4 (28.9,59.4)

Figure S1. a. Average monthly precipitation, b. average monthly temperature, in La Junta, Lamar, and Las Animas, Colorado, from 2012-2022. La Junta, Lamar, and Las Animas are three of the nearest cities to the study site, located approximately 53 km from the study site.

Supplemental Information 1. Distance sampling is a proven method for estimating abundance

in arthropods (Clark 2016; Mathis *et al.* 2024; Royale *et al.* 1982; Thomas *et al.* 2010). Distance sampling models estimate animal density (D) with the equation (Miller 2016):

$$D = \frac{n}{(2wLP_a)}$$

Where n = the number of observations, w = the width of the area around the transect that surveying was performed, L = the length of the transect, and P = the probability of finding a burrow at the site (Miller 2016; Thompson *et al.* 1994).

Distance sampling operates on the concept that the further away from a transect an animal is, the more difficult it is to detect (Clark 2016; Miller 2016; Royale *et al.* 1982; Thompson *et al.* 1994). The detection function ($g(x)$), a key component of distance analysis, gives the probability of an animal being detected at x distance from the transect (Clark 2016; Royale *et al.* 1982; Thomas *et al.* 2010). DISTANCE uses several key functions (uniform, half-normal, hazard rate, and negative exponential) and adjustment

types (cosine, simple polynomial, and hermite polynomial) to fit the curve of the detection function to a relative frequency histogram of the observed distances of the target animals to the transect line (Miller 2016; Royale *et al.* 1982; Thompson *et al.* 1994).